

ANALYTICAL STUDY OF VASCULAR NETWORKS FOR SELF-HEALING COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

A qualitative study on the influence of an embedded vascular network on the structural performance of a FRP composite laminate is presented. This study includes: methods of forming such vascular networks in laminates; characterisation of laminate cross-sections; FE analysis for failure initiation and validation of the FE results via mechanical testing.

Keywords: self-healing, biomimetic, finite element analysis, vascular network, composite materials, fibre reinforced polymers

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are renowned for their high strength, high stiffness and extraordinary lightweight. Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) are gradually taking the place of conventional metal alloy materials for some or most of the primary structures in modern aircraft and are the key in determining reliability, performance, gross weight and cost effectiveness of the system [1]. In such high-end applications, any minor defect or imperfection within the composite material, whether introduced during manufacturing or operational life, may result in significant reduction of overall performance. Such defects may be difficult to detect visually and, furthermore, result in costly repair and maintenance work. The idea of self-healing may provide an alternative approach to addressing this problem. The underlying concept of self-healing is analogous to the healing process in living organisms, i.e. to repair the internal damage by using the materials already contained within the structure [2]. Researchers in various fields [3, 4, 5, 6] have successfully developed discrete bioinspired methods to provide autonomous repair functionality to targeted material systems, e.g. bulk polymers, FRP composites, etc., through liquid based self-healing systems. However, such approaches are constrained by limited supply of healing agent stored within the structure and hence failure to heal multiple damage events occurring at the same location.

To address this problem, a concept for the next generation of self-healing composite materials is proposed. The philosophy behind this is to take a biomimetic step forward to implement a pervasive vascular network system that has the potential to deliver healing agent from single or limited resource to all locations in the structure as well as providing continuous healing to repeated damage events [2, 7]. Successful preliminary studies on such a biomimetic self-healing concept have been accomplished [8, 9] by embedding miniature interconnected vascular networks in either pure polymeric materials or core materials of composite sandwich structures. The inclusion of the

healing vascular networks does not disrupt the internal structure of these homogeneous materials as the polymer can easily flow around and incorporate the embedded entities. However, this is not the case in advanced FRP composite laminates. The presence of such inclusions can disturb the composite laminate architecture, e.g. in-plane and out-of-plane fibre alignments, and can have significant effect upon overall structural performance.

As a consequence, an ongoing project at the University of Bristol aims to investigate the form of conceptual self-healing vascular network designs within a FRP composite laminate, as well as evaluating the implications for composite mechanical performance of including such networks whilst also assessing their ability to contribute to a self-healing system. The conceptual design of self-healing vascular networks is divided into two different scale categories: the vasculature cross-sectional shape (micro scale) and the plan-form vascular pattern (macro scale), respectively. Aspects of the research concerning the former category are presented in this paper. It is unlikely to be able to embed an interconnected vascular network into a FRP composite laminate without having certain sections of the network being oriented off-axis to the local fibre direction(s) of adjacent plies. When a vasculature with a dimension much greater than a typical reinforcing fibre is embedded off-axis to the local fibre orientation it results in geometric distortion of the surrounding fibres and creation of *resin-rich pockets* (Fig. 1). Such resin pockets are regarded as potential defects within the structural laminate [10]. This study focuses on the case where the vasculature orientation is perpendicular to local fibre direction (i.e. an extreme case for off-axis vasculatures) as this is regarded as being the most detrimental case for the structural integrity of host composite laminates.

Fig.1. (left) Micrograph of circular vasculature forming a resin-rich pocket; (centre) Idealized model with vasculature at centre; (right) Quarter-section FEA model.

Since both the shape and size of a *circular* vasculature (in this study diameter = 315 μm) are similar to a fibre optic sensor (FOS), previous studies on the influence of embedding FOS into FRP composite laminates are regarded as good comparators [e.g. 10, 11, 12, 13]. Detailed analytical and experimental studies of a single circular vasculature as well as other single vascular forms are presented in a separate paper (R.S. Trask *et al.* ICCM17, 2009). Advancing from the single circular vasculature, several different vascular geometries have been considered for their feasibility as self-healing vasculatures in this study. To date, most of the healing agents (e.g. epoxy resins) used for self-healing composite materials have been two-part systems [14]. In order to store such multiple component systems, multi-sectioned vasculatures, which consist of two or more sub-sections to form an integral vasculature, have been investigated. A novel biomimetic vascular concept which achieves such multiple component vasculatures has been derived which mimics the design of “ray cell” type structures in ring porous hardwoods [15, 16] (Fig. 2). Such “ray structure”

forms of vasculature may provide a conservative design for imparting a self-healing function based on multi-component healing agents. Proof-of-concept designs of such ray structure vasculature have been developed at the University of Bristol. With careful arrangement of sizes and pattern of sub-vasculature, the resin pocket geometry of ray cell vasculature behaves little differently from that of single circular vasculature. Hence embedding a ray cell vasculature does not necessarily result in much greater penalty upon overall mechanical performance than embedding a single circular vasculature.

This paper presents a qualitative study on the influence of vasculature (especially the ray cell form) upon the mechanical performance of the host material. Methods of forming proof-of-concept types of “ray structure” vasculature in laminates are proposed. Extensive micrographs have been used to characterise the laminate cross-sectional geometries, especially at the resin pocket region. FE modelling results of stress analysis at this region while the laminate is under static load are presented, and likely failure initiation mechanisms are proposed based on FE results. Finally, in-plane compressive tests were conducted to qualitatively confirm the failure initiation mechanisms deduced from FEA results.

Fig. 2 (left) Image of a ray structure vasculature in ring porous hardwood [15]; (right) Idealized model of ray structure vasculature for FEA, consisting of 10 sub-vasculature levels

METHODOLOGY OF SPECIMEN MANUFACTURING AND CHARACTERISATION

Specimens of unidirectional (UD) carbon/epoxy composite laminates were made containing various types of vasculature, single or multiple, along the mid-plane. The laminates were made using 24 plies of unidirectional IM7/8552 prepreg tape manufactured by Hexcel Inc. (HexPly 8552). The vasculature-forming material used was stainless steel wires commercially available in sizes ranging from 50 μ m. A thin PTFE film was applied by spraying to the stainless steel wires to assist their later removal from cured laminates. The stainless steel wires were introduced between the plies, located at the mid-length, during lay-up of the uncured prepreg stack. The wires were aligned perpendicular to the fibre orientation and extended over the entire width of the specimens. A small amount of tension was applied to the steel wires to ensure their straightness. The prepregs were vacuum bagged and cured in autoclave following manufacturer's suggested cycle. After the prepregs were cured, the steel wires were removed from the laminates by manual pulling, leaving hollow-channel vasculature in the laminates. Unwanted laminate edges were trimmed, and then the laminates were cut to the compression test specimen size of 90mm (fibre direction) by 10mm (width) by 3mm (thickness), following requirements in the Imperial Collage Compression Test Method

[17]. Small sections of laminates containing each vascular type were potted separately in epoxy resin, polished and micrographed for further characterisation of laminate cross-sections.

Forming of the “ray cell” vasculures is the more challenging step in the manufacturing process. To date, ray cell vasculatures of up to three sub-vascule levels have been created. Stainless steel wires were manually bound together at both ends by nylon threads, following the designed pattern in the idealized model (Fig. 2) and then laid on the mid-plane of prepreg stack. Although fully-developed 10-level ray structure, as shown in Fig. 2, is currently not achievable due to limitation on available techniques, the ray cell forms of up to three levels (Fig. 3) will provide an indication of likely crack initiation and progression pathways.

Cross-sectional microscopic pictures of ray structure vasculures in level 1, 2 and 3, respectively, are presented in Fig. 3. Single circular vasculures (Fig. 1) are regarded as level 0 in a ray structure system. The dimensions of each ray cell level are: level 0 (largest at the centre) - 500 μ m; level 1 - 315 μ m; level 2 - 150 μ m and level 3 - 150 μ m and 200 μ m, respectively. As illustrated in Fig. 3, parameters of cross-sectional geometries for each vascule type were quantified from the micrographs, which include: resin pocket length, fibre disturbance angle, fibre disturbance height (i.e. through-the-thickness distance from centre of embedded vascule to end of laminate layer which are disturbed/bent due to the presence of embedded entity). These parameters were used for geometry construction in subsequent FE modelling.

Fig. 3 (top left) Micrograph of ray cell level 1; (top right) Micrograph of ray cell level 2; (bottom left) Micrograph of ray cell level 3; (bottom right) Resin pocket parameters

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND FAILURE INITIATIONS

Finite Element Modelling Methodology

All geometric parameters in the FE models are based on actual microscopic observations and are normalized by the radius of centre vascule, R . The observed resin pocket length, L_{RP} , ranges from $7.15R$ to $8.9R$ depending on the vascule type; and fibre disturbance height, h_d , from $2.5R$ to $3.4R$, respectively. Since model geometry and applied in-plane load are symmetric, only one quarter of the model is used, as shown in Fig. 1 with centre of central vascule being taken as the origin. The specimen width is very large compared to its thickness, hence the model is assumed to be in a plane strain state. The width, the thickness and the length (or fibre direction) are taken as x -, y - and z -axes, respectively. The curved lines in Fig. 1 represent the profile of disturbed reinforcing fibres due to embedded vascules, which are geometrically distributed as per the micrographs. The fibre orientations in curved area are varied to follow the shape of resin pocket and gradually change parallel to the x -axis. The FE models are modelled with 8-node plain strain elements (CPE8) using a commercial FE code ABAQUS 6.7-1. The isoparametric mapping concept is used to map the model while extra care was taken when meshing the interested regions such as vascule boundaries and resin pocket run-outs. The datasheets for material properties of IM7/8552 unidirectional CFRP and neat resin are taken from [18, 19]. Symmetric boundary conditions are applied. The end $x=48R$ is loaded by uniform displacement in the x - equivalent to 1% strain. Linear elastic analysis is performed and complete stress and strain contours (max and min principal) are calculated.

Finite Element Analysis Results of Single Circular Vascules

Analytical results of single circular vascule (Fig. 4) show that, while the structure is under axial compressive load, the highest *tensile* stress in the through-the-thickness direction occurs at the vascular boundary (i.e. point C, or 3 o'clock position) with a stress concentration factor of 0.203; and highest compressive stress at the resin pocket run-out region (i.e. point A). The through-the-thickness tensile stresses are regarded as the main cause of crack initiation within conventional FRP laminates [12]. Hence it can be deduced that internal crack may be initiated at the vascular boundary (3 o'clock position) when the structure is under axial compression. On the contrary, under axial tensile load, the highest *tensile* through-the-thickness stress occurs at the resin pocket run-out region (point A). The deduced failure mechanism under axial compression (Fig. 4) indicates that the vascules will be fractured before structural failure. This is potentially beneficial for a self-healing system based on vascular networks. With the propagation of cracks towards both ends of a resin pocket, the structure will finally fail due to fibre micro-buckling. To this end, the stored self-healing agents have the potential to heal the crack and terminate/delay the structural failure process.

Fig. 4. (left) Transverse stress contours of single circular vasculature (global & local views); (right) Deduced failure mechanism under compressive loading

Finite Element Analysis Results of “Ray Structure” Vasculures

To obtain a clearer indication of the likely crack propagation path within the resin pocket region, as well as to fulfil a requirement to be able to store multiple component healing agent systems, the biomimetic “ray structure” vasculature has been analysed. Fig. 5 shows the FEA results of the resin pocket region of a ray structure level 3 and level 10, respectively. An enlarged image of the max stress regions is inserted. FEA results indicate that the “ray cell” vasculature geometry increases the probability of crack interaction within the vasculures (i.e. vascular ligaments) before structural failure. This is a key requirement for such multi-component healing agents to perform any effective self-healing function upon host materials. Furthermore, the structural failure initiation mechanism is not adversely affected; that is, after fracturing the vascular ligaments the cracks still propagate towards resin pocket ends and finally result in structural failure due to fibre micro-buckling. It can thus be concluded that, with some penalties in terms of increased stress concentration factors, the “ray cell” form of vasculature provides a conservative design for imparting a self-healing function.

Fig. 5. Transverse stress contours of “ray cell” vasculature (local view only)

MECHANICAL TESTS

Experimental Features

The compression tests were conducted in a 100-kN Instron mechanical test machine at under displacement control at 1mm/min. Detailed compression rig set-up is illustrated in [17]. For each vascule type, 8-10 specimens were tested and the load-displacement results were recorded by the controlling software and averaged afterwards.

In order to capture the very moment of crack initiation, a Photron Fastcam SA1 high speed digital video camera (8GB memory) has been employed. The recording frame rate was 150000fps, which provides a total record time of 2.24 seconds. In normal conditions such elapse time and frame rate are enough for capturing the whole process from crack initiation to final failure. Manual triggering was used for the test due to lack of built-in connection between high speed camera and test machine to enable automatic triggering.

Compression Test Results of Single Circular Vasculures

Twelve single circular vascule specimens were tested under compression loading while being recorded by high speed camera; nine of them have shown the same crack initiation and final failure behaviour. The average recording period of the camera is 1.8 seconds. With the high speed camera images shown in Fig. 6 it can be clearly affirmed that the cracks were initiated at the vascular boundary (3 o'clock position). The experimental results of crack initiation, crack propagation and final failure all correspond well to the predictions based on FEA findings. The “knee” in the load-displacement plot recorded by test machine clearly indicates the occurrence of first crack. The specimens all failed by buckling, and have V-shaped or oblique fracture surfaces.

Fig. 6 (left) Failure images of single circular vascule captured at a frame rate of 150000fps; (right) Load-displacement plot (insert: plot of enlarged peak area) of a representative compressive loading test.

Compression Test Results of “Ray Structure” Vasculures

Eight-ten specimens of level 1, 2 and 3 ray structure vasculatures, respectively, were tested in compression experiments. Approximately 90% of the tests for each ray cell vasculature have shown similar behaviour with regard to crack initiation, propagation and failure. High speed camera images of ray cell level 1 are shown in Fig. 7. The locally enlarged image of vasculature region in Frame #3 depicts the moment of crack initiation at the vascular ligament, though the resolution is less than perfect due to restrictions on capacities of high speed camera and corresponding lens. After the initiation stage, the cracks follow similar paths to the single circular vasculature cases, propagating towards resin pocket ends; and the structure finally fails by buckling. Similar mechanisms were found in other ray cell vasculature levels though the ray cell patterns differ. These results have soundly confirmed the failure predictions made with the FEA.

Fig. 7. Failure images of level 1 ray cell vasculature captured at frame rate of 150000fps

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A preliminary study on the next generation self-healing composite materials embedded with biomimetic vascular networks has been presented. A novel biomimetic idea of “ray structure” vasculature form has been proposed. Several engineering ray structure vascular forms have been developed and manufactured, and the laminate cross-sectional geometries containing the resin pocket and such vasculures were observed. FE modelling results have shown that under compressive load, the crack will be initiated at the boundary of a *single circular vasculature* at a 3 o’clock position and propagate towards the end of a resin pocket while further loading is applied. Final failure occurs due to fibre micro-buckling. For ray structure vasculatures under compressive load, the ligaments in between sub-vasculures are ruptured before the crack propagates across the entire ray cell and towards the resin pocket ends. In this case, the opportunity arises for components of multiple-part healing agents to mix with each other before bleeding out and healing the structure. Mechanical testing results recorded by high speed camera have validated the FE model predictions.

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